

QBÀTÁLA RELIGIOUS GROUP AMONG THE YORUBA OF ILÉ-IFÈ

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QBÀTÁLA RELIGIOUS GROUP AMONG THE YORUBA OF ILÉ-IFÈ The Qbàtálá religious group forms one of the cardinal traditional religious groups among the Yoruba in southwestern Nigeria. Just like most other groups, it is affiliated with one of the primordial deities in the Yoruba pantheon. Qbàtálá is also called Ọ̀rìsà rílá. Qbàtálá is believed among the Yoruba of Ile-Ife to be the arch divinity whom Olódùmarè (the Supreme Being in Yoruba cosmology) saddled with the responsibility of creation of all that exists. It was noted that Qbàtálá overindulged himself in drinking palm wine, he then stepped aside to drink wine which resulted in him sleeping off. Having slept off, another deity Odùduwà picked up the item and proceeded to carry out the assignment having heard Olódùmarè while instructing Qbàtálá. When Qbàtálá woke from his sleep, he discovered the situation and forbade himself and his children from ever taking palm wine. As a result, members of the group are forbidden from drinking palm wine. Another version of the Yoruba mythology notes that despite his failure in creating the universe, he was still responsible for the creation of humans. The Yoruba people believe that Olódùmarè has much trust in Qbàtálá's creativity and capacity. Therefore, He did not commit much time into supervising and inspecting the humans he moulded before breathing life into them. The myth states that Qbàtálá's negligence resulted in creating some humans with deformities. The Yoruba classify albinos, one legged, hunchback, blind and other physical disabilities as deformities resulting from Qbàtálá's defective creation. This act, the Yoruba traditionally hold as being responsible for the existence of people with different disabilities. In Yoruba parlance therefore, individuals with physical disabilities are referred to as ẹ̀ni Ọ̀rìsà which means the people of Ọ̀rìsà (Qbàtálá being the Ọ̀rìsà). The group believes that Qbàtálá being the arch divinity embraces all other deities. This is demonstrated with the presence of shrines dedicated to some other deities in Qbàtálá compound. Qbàtálá is regarded as the essence of justice, purity, and clear thinking. He is wisdom personified and also represents cleanliness and calmness. His wisdom and cleanness results in his use of a white robe which is also replicated by members of the group. While his adherents are permitted to use other colours, places such as shrines that are considered sacred among the group can only be accessed by individuals arrayed in white clothing alone. The group's adherence to cleanliness as exemplified in Qbàtálá also makes it sacrosanct for anyone who would enter the compound or the palace of Qbàtálá in Igbó-Ìtápá in Ilé-Ife to put off their shoes at the gate before entry. The group worships Qbàtálá following the Yoruba indigenous (traditional) calendar which comprises five days each week. The group also observes vigils. The Qbàtálá worshipers have houses built as palaces and halls for worship among others. The group also established schools like Qbàtálá Nursery and Primary School, Igbó-Ìtápá, Ilé-Ife where indigenous knowledge (Ọ̀rìsà related topics) and western education subjects are taught. The group also 'has shrines where sacrifices are offered to Qbàtálá. It is believed that children of Qbàtálá are easily prone to stress and deadlines which often result in mental stress. However, this is often taken care of with the purchase of two coconuts, one will be offered to Qbàtálá while two holes will be punched in the other through which the fluid inside the coconut will be poured into a cup and applied into the person's scalp for some hours or overnight. The group maintains that once this is done, the individual will surely recover due to the calming effects of the procedure.

Date Range: 1900 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Ife

Region tags: Western Africa, Ile-Ife, Africa, Osun state, Nigeria, Southwest Nigeria

Ile-Ife is the ancestral home of the Yoruba race

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Neimark, John Philip. *The Way of the Orisa: Empowering Your Life Through the Ancient African Religion of Ifa*. San Francisco: HarperCollins Publishers, 1993.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: [The Obatala Factor in Yoruba History | History in Africa | Cambridge Core](#)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://fb.watch/rmtWGC9veS/>
- Source 1 Description: Facebook link showing video of Qbàtálá worshippers singing and dancing during Qbàtálá festival in 2023

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: They are competitive in the sense that they are found in the geographical location with other religious groups which seek to recruit members from the same population.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is accommodating in the sense that different religious groups operate within the same social space without records of violent conflicts in the region.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The cultural contact is actively seeking expansion.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Violence is avoided, if there is a need for any confrontation, the cultural contact usually seeks redress in the court of law.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Religious groups are generally family-based. However, divination is also made to determine religious groups in some instances.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals are free to take a decision on joining the group whenever it suits them.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

- Yes [specify]: In the event an individual is confronted with life crisis, they consult Obatala or Ifa priests who through the process of divination determine the cause of their crisis and proffer solution to the problem which, many times, involves prescription of worship of some given deity who specialises in proffering solutions to their kind of problems. It is important to stress that there are diverse ways of procuring solutions even to similar conditions or circumstances. By implication of the solved problems, many individuals have become members/adherents of the religious groups within the region.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

- No

Does the religion have official political support

- No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

- No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

- Estimated population, numeric: 15000

Notes: cannot be less than 15000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

- Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.18

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

- Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: Not small but a brand of Yoruba indigenous religion

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

- Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

- Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: The leader is regarded as the leader of Obatala worshippers in Ile-Ife and its environs.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 1

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: From encounters and experience

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: From one's parent or guardians who possessed great deal of power

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Power could be transmitted from the deity to the leader.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: One teacher could also pass some power to his or her apprentices.

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: In certain instances, some powers are needed to function effectively in some offices. such powers are either passed down from the previous leader or transmitted to the person from the deity or through certain rituals.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: In most cases, other leaders make the appointment through divination, but at

times the deity also chooses for itself.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The group makes use of oral traditions encoded in proverbs, songs, adages, etc.

↳ Are they written:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: In many instances, stories of ancient incidences are told and certain material facts are extracted from the stories. These facts are energised spiritually and become potent words which are deployed to achieve certain predetermined ends; both positively and negatively.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The priests and their trainees are custodians of the oral scriptures and do interpret them

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– I don't know

Notes: It is uncommon for the non-initiate to understand and interpret the oral scriptures of the Yoruba Traditional Religious groups.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– I don't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 5

Notes: Ile-Ife is a very fast community with many features which includes large settlements, educational institutions, and other religious groups.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 400

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 100

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 10

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 15

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Grooves, palaces, shrines

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Sites like grooves and shrines are often protected from the public with trees which as a result preserve the cosmos.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the spirit goes back to Olodumare (The Supreme Being) at death.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Interviewees claim no one ever died and return to life. therefore, what happens after death is unknown.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Field claims once one is dead that is the end

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: This is done for members of the community to see the deceased for the last time and is often accompanied by singing, drumming, dancing, and feasting.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Usually classified as proper burial which is mostly characterised by celebrations of the life lived by the deceased.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: The prominence of the individual within the group could call for special ritual and ceremony before the corpse will be handed over to the family member for proper burial.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: This is dependent on the instruction the deceased gave before passing and divination.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: For Instance, a renown sculptural artist could be buried with some of his work

items.

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: This is dependent on the deceased, divination or the discretion of the members of the family.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Could include work implements/instruments if the individual is highly prolific in the occupation.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Individual could also be buried in his personal room or any other room they chose while alive.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the existence of supernatural beings.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the existence of Olodumare, the supreme being.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Omniscent, Omnipresent, Generous, loving, etc.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: such as good and evil
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
 - Notes: the other gods are considered to be his subordinates
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: He can manifest in other forms especially through his divinities or natural features such as wind, rivers, thunder trees, etc.
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Yes but through other means as well

↳ Only through monarch

– Yes

Notes: Through other means as well

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme god can also communicate through animals and trees, rocks, etc.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Human spirit has knowledge of matters that concern them.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: Group believes that the human spirit's knowledge is limited outside the sample region.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– No

Notes: The group believes the human spirit cannot exhibit an impact.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The group notes that those who claim to offer sacrifice to their dead parent do not see the dead parent eat the food they offered.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within

the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - No
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - Yes [specify]: No specific organization. The group are mainly Obatala worshippers, however, they make sacrifices to other divinities on matters concerning their jurisprudences.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The group recognises that supernatural monitoring is present and they teach members to be careful what actions, words and thoughts they allow so they do not incur the wrath of the almighty.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural beings, especially the deities have actions, foods and other things they forbid their followers from having contact with. The adherents are therefore careful as they refrain from such things as engaging in them would expose them to danger in the hands of the deities.

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Sacred space

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is forbidden among the followers of the group. It does not matter if it is the murder of children, adults or strangers.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - No
 - Notes: Except in cases of the person being bestowed to the supernatural being
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings hold matters of integrity in high esteem.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: it is often said that the deities do not bless anyone who does not have an occupation neither do they bless an indolent fellow.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings forbid taking risks, especially at the expense of life.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Especially one done with negative intentions.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings despise stealing irrespective of the degree.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Especially prescribed ones.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings care about the truthfulness and commitment of members of the groups and do not have concern for non-member.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings forbid cheating others and seek to economic wellbeing of the members of the group.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Obatala is an emblem of cleanliness and expects the same from his followers.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes that supernatural beings care about people who are trustworthy and those who freely express love unfeigned to one another.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Through the divinities

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: through natural or artificial disaster

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes the cause could be determined through divination.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: It is often targeted to teach a lesson. The lesson might be towards religious ethics or personal adherence to good life.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: The group believes that punishments are meted out here on earth. They believe people often receive rewards for their deeds before they die and reiterated that no one knows what happens after death.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that punishment could include the death of one's children. These punishments are often dependent on the nature of the person's offense.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– No

Notes: More often not specifically known and not investigated. However, is often attached to the fellow's known good deeds.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The group believe people receive their rewards here on earth. Also, they do not know what happens to anyone after death.

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The group believes seeing several generations of their children is a reward for living a good life.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: The group has taboos which must be strictly observed by the adherents. There are also clear social norms which followers, especially religious professionals must pay close attention to.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: This happens sometimes when obedience to social norms are linked to the pleasure or the command of deities

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes

- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: Love is the most emphasised moral issue among the group

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Celibacy is not encouraged nor practiced in the religious group.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

Notes: Males are allowed to marry more than one wife at a time in the group.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Women are not allowed to marry more than one husband at a time in the group

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: No man is expected to be involved in sexual relations with another man, an animal or their blood relations.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: No woman is expected to be involved in sexual relations with another woman, an animal or their blood relations.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Palm wine, jute leaves, etc. Palm wine is the most prominent of what an adherent of Obatala must not take.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice is allowed in the religious group

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice is allowed in the religious group

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Suicide is forbidden among adherents of the religious group.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: The group preaches love towards all humans irrespective of religious affiliation.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 0

Notes: There is no general rule of required interval time

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 20

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 0

Notes: There is no general prescription of required interval time.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: This can be carried out by the leader if the performance is not being performed by him or her. To ascertain that due processes are being followed.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Notes: Only in rare cases would simultaneous occurrence of events be necessary.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: Obatala is majorly found among the Yoruba in Southwestern Nigeria and around the globe.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: The group is not comprised of very wealthy individuals. They are people struggling to eke out a living so they are not economically empowered to provide institutionalised famine relief.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide institutionalised care for the elderly and infirm. However, each family has a duty to take care of their elderly and infirm among them.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: The group established an educational institution which goes by the name Obatala Nursery and Primary School in Igbo-Itapa, Ile-Ife. The essence of the establishment is to provide educational opportunities for its members where they can learn Western education disciplines and Orisa related matters.

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the group also encourages its members to pursue education to whatever level they deem fit.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The government institutions and available all around.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The group members interact with government bureaucracies around them. This includes educational institutions, local authority administrations (local governments) and several other ministries, departments and agencies of government.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: Irrigation and flood control are capital intensive projects which the religious group cannot finance nor provide for itself or the polity.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government at different levels provided transportation infrastructure to the community which the group adherents benefit from.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the State levies all adult citizens of living within their territory. This includes members of this religious group.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The State Police Force has jurisdiction in the community.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The State Judicial System has jurisdiction over the community.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: If it is established that the properties were acquired through fraudulent means, the individual may have to forfeit such properties.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subject to the legal code provided by the State.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the military provided by the State

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: They adopt the use of the Yoruba language which is the indigenous language of their community.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yoruba language is the medium of communication.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yoruba language which is the language used generally in the community is also the medium of communication among members of the religious group.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group operate with the Gregorian calendar in use in the country.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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